

Towards Certifiable AI in Medicine: Illustrated for Multi-label ECG Classification Performance Metrics

This repository contains comprehensive information complementing the corresponding paper *Towards Certifiable AI in Medicine: Illustrated for Multi-label ECG Classification Performance Metrics* (link will be added as soon as it is published). The folder “Results_Metrics_Selection” contains the evaluation of our experimental results regarding reliable performance evaluation metrics for multi-label electrocardiogram (ECG) classification. The folder “QG_Process_Structure” and its subfolders illustrate the lifecycle integration of the introduced and empirically extracted approach for machine learning (ML) design decision making as part of the exemplary documentation centered around our generic and customizable methodology based on Quality Gates towards certifiable AI in medicine.¹ This setup intends to define at what stage, which design decisions are relevant, and when they should be revisited, while providing a structure for (automatable) documentation to achieve a comprehensive risk management. Our proposed generic and customizable methodology is intended to be extended in a practical way based on (groups of) medical use cases with further research.

First, our experimental results (1) as well as their basic setup (2) are briefly introduced. Next, the accompanying folder structure (3) is embedded within the context of our methodology and finally, the empirically extracted method towards ML design decision making (4) is outlined.

1. Experiments – Results

The experiments are intended to derive applicable guidelines for a trustworthy metrics selection illustrated for ECG multi-label classification. Their results and evaluation are included in the accompanying folder “Results_Metrics_Selection”. On a process-level, the experimental structure is embedded within our methodology, as explained in the following section. Since the experiments are based on the open-source Physionet data² – a ready-to-use ML data set with a well-known distribution, the data is not explored further in a practical manner – except for the label structure. The empirical results are explained in more detail in the respective files that are introduced in more detail in the corresponding paper, where the overall approach and medical setting are explained, as well.

Overall, a use case-adapted compilation of multiple metrics is necessary for a comprehensive evaluation. We present a metrics compilation that consists of the most known and widely used classification metrics, which we believe can be applied as foundation or point of reference for other use cases and based on the tuning objective and medical setting other/new metrics can be added analogously. Regarding binary-based multi-label classification performance metrics combined with high data imbalance and a ‘meaningless’ negative class (absence of a label), the following generalizable tendencies can be deduced based on our experiments:

- Macro-averaged metrics are most reliable, they treat all labels equally and are not influenced by label support in the data set
- Receiver Operating Characteristic Area under the Curve (ROC AUC) should be referenced with caution since it behaves very optimistic compared to the prediction vs. groundtruth label distribution and appears to not accurately mirror the model’s confidence
- Precision Recall Area under the Curve (PR AUC) appears to mirror the model’s confidence more realistically

¹ M. Elia et al., A methodology based on quality gates for certifiable AI in medicine: towards a reliable application of metrics in machine learning, ICISOFT, 2023.

² https://github.com/physionetchallenges/evaluation2021/blob/main/dx_mapping_unscored.csv

- Addressing label correlations that exist in the real world is crucial for binary based multi-label classification. We adapted a domain-embedded approach³ to integrate label correlations based on a benefit matrix to our use case that can be optimized further

The hypothesis that should be tested next, is whether our findings are applicable to any binary based multi-label use case that is characterized by a high data imbalance and the negative class of the averaged binary case has no practical meaning⁴ as with our use case situated in emergency medical care. Further, based on our tuning objective, F1-Score is the metric that should be monitored during training to optimize the desired results even though its impact amounts to only a few percentage points. It balances Precision and Recall, the two metrics that mirror most our real-world objective based on the predicted label distribution. Supplementary metrics that project similar perspectives are Specificity and False-Positive-Rate (FPR). Additional metrics to analyze the label distribution in more detail include Jaccard-Score and Matthews-Correlation Coefficient (MCC), as well as PR AUC to analyze the model's confidence. Finally, more data, especially for rare labels is necessary, since as our experiments have shown, some labels are not sufficiently represented in the data to achieve a reasonable measurement. However, based on the real-world distribution, luckily healthy people outweigh and other means to address data imbalance should be considered in parallel. For instance, regarding performance metrics, imbalance can be addressed through threshold post-processing when calculating confusion matrix-based metrics, as in the present research. This method necessitates to be updated in line with the data set's dynamic distribution.

The following research questions were focus of our experiments centered around performance metrics and more comprehensive information on our results is contained in the complementary folders.

1. Label support in data set
 - a. Proportional split > mirrors Physionet data distribution
 - b. Comparison of 20 more fine-grained and 8 more compact labels
 - c. Introduction of *container-labels* to elevate support and mirror the medical use case
2. Metrics Compilation
 - a. Selection
 - b. Domain-embedded interpretation
3. ROC AUC vs. PR AUC
 - a. Expressiveness and applicability
4. Multi-label averaging
 - a. Expressiveness and applicability
5. Metric-to-monitor during training
 - a. Focus on F1- vs. Fbeta-Score (macro-averaged)
6. Post-processing thresholding methods
 - a. Comparison of FIXED (0.5) vs. CIST³ vs. PR vs. ROC Thresholding

2. Experiments – Setup

We applied a basic setup for our experiments, since the focus lies on process extraction and analysis of interrelated tendencies concerning ML performance metrics, rather than a profound performance optimization. Our experiments are implemented based on the open-source framework LIFEDATA⁵ and our model architecture is adapted from Xu et al.⁶ It consists of a combination of bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory and Convolutional Neural Networks. The experiments are run based on a proportional, stratified split into 70% train, 10% validation and 20% test data. This guarantees an equal

³ Y. Liu et al., Automatic Multi-Label ECG Classification with Category Imbalance and Cost-Sensitive Thresholding, Biosensors, 2021.

⁴ An exception is the label *norm* that refers to a healthy patient. The negative label signifies that something is wrong with the patient. However, due to time-sensitivity of some abnormalities, this information is not enough in an emergency setting.

⁵ F. Stieler et al., LIFEDATA - a framework for traceable active learning projects, IEEE (REW), 2023.

⁶ X. Xu et al., Interpretation of Electrocardiogram (ECG) Rhythm by Combined CNN and biLSTM, IEEE Access, 2020.

label distribution among the different subsets, which ensures that rare labels are represented in each set. Further, this approach incorporates the underlying data set's distribution, in our case the Physionet data, which impacts the model's performance depending on the relation between the *known* data during development and the *new* data it encounters after deployment in the real world. However, based on our fictional setting, the evaluation of such considerations is beyond the scope of this part of the AI lifecycle flow. During training, early stopping was integrated and duration limited to maximum 50 epochs with a batch size of 32. Other hyperparameters were adapted to Liu et al.,³ i.e. the initial learning rate of 0.001 with Exponential Decay, Adam Optimizer and Binary Cross Entropy Loss.

3. Folder structure – Quality Gates along the lifecycle

Among others, a thorough documentation of AI lifecycle design decisions and their definition is mandatory for audits of intelligent systems in medicine. With the objective of achieving long-term (semi-)automation, documentation can be structured in alignment with the generic lifecycle flow.⁷ This is mirrored by the accompanying folder “QG_Process_Structure” and its subfolders in an exemplary manner. Overall, the presented setup intends to define at what stage, which design decisions are relevant, and when they should be revisited in accordance with other design decisions from a horizontal and vertical perspective. Our methodology is intended to serve as a foundation for the research community and the industry to structure information on (groups of) medical use cases and result in concrete guidelines that are intended to be continuously extended and tested by the research community. We aim to propose a generic and customizable concept to collect and create concrete approaches for trustworthy AI lifecycle management in form of QGs, since the outlined project is enormous to complete for every existing medical use case and data type.

Consequently, the proposed folder structure aims to illustrate the global QG organization along the AI lifecycle flow processes, while providing an option to include the system's evolution,⁸ since AI models can continuously learn and evolve. The presented setup provides a structure for (automatable) documentation to achieve a comprehensive and continuous risk management, which is a fundamental part of our proposed methodology. It is illustrated in detail on GitHub. Especially, the *Lifecycle – Development – Evaluation* section contains related QGs that are based on this contribution.

<https://github.com/miriamelia/MQG4AI>

Concretely, the introduced planning structure mirrors the AI lifecycle flow starting with the generic high-level QGs. Their definition is based on the development of comprehensive concepts for AI lifecycle processes under consideration of regulatory requirements tailored to specific use cases with individual tuning objectives, data, and medical knowledge, for instance. The identified procedures propagate relevant information towards low-level QGs and use case-specific low-level QGs are defined in accordance with high-level QGs. For instance, the chosen model architecture depends on the intended use, which impacts other design decisions, as well. Further, the development of an overall concept for QG Model of multi-label ECG classification under consideration which design decisions can be generalized and to what extent is part of our proposed methodology.

In the present research, we focus on the low-level *QG Performance Evaluation Metrics* that contributes to the required risk mitigation in the grand scheme of QG Model through reliable performance metrics, specifically for multi-label (ECG) classification. An incorrect ML model evaluation can harm the patient and poses a risk which is analyzed in further detail from a medical perspective for the design of our emergency setting adjusted label structure and benefit matrix. The proposed method for QG

⁷ International Standards Organization, ISO/IEC FDIS 5338:2023(E) on AI system lifecycle processes, 2023.

⁸ Different deployed versions are described as a next evolution of the intelligent system, comparable with an update for a specific software, for instance.

Performance Evaluation Metrics creation will be explained in the next section in more detail. It consists of the three stages pre-, intra-, and post-selection and is referenced as part of the proposed folder structure. Finally, lifecycle inherent interdependencies between QGs are intended to be included, as illustrated in an exemplary manner for *QG Performance Evaluation Metrics (QG Metrics)* regarding *QG Data* as well as *QG Deployment* and *QG Maintenance*.

The presented setup is not complete but rather illustrates the overall idea how to realize QGs and their documentation along the AI lifecycle flow for a specific use case. For instance, interdependencies with other *QG Model Development* specific design decisions are not highlighted explicitly and methods for their integration are beyond the scope of the present research.

4. Low-level QG creation – pre-, intra-, and post-Selection (Template versions)

In general, empirical method development is an essential component of QG creation as part of our proposed methodology, aiming to extract standardizable approaches. Especially so, since currently certifiable AI is in its infancy and the concrete realization of design decisions depends heavily on the respective use case. Once more standardized methods for concrete design decisions are established for (groups of) use cases, method creation becomes more organized, and depending on the project and process stage, a fitting method can be selected from the pool of identified approaches. Our generalizable method towards AI design decision making can be generalized as follows:

The derived approach structured into dynamic pre-, intra-, and post-selection stages is intended to be adapted to other QG Model related design decisions such as QG Loss Function or QG Model Architecture. Its applicability to other low-level QGs that are assigned to different high-level QGs needs to be evaluated in further detail.

Pre-Selection builds on previous findings, and possibly other as relevant identified QGs. It aims to implement the first setup (or select different candidate approaches to be tested in parallel) for the respective design decision as a baseline for further internal optimization throughout the lifecycle. Above all, this includes a profound understanding of the respective use case, which is crucial for a reliable concretization of design decisions. This information is provided by the high-level QG Data and QG Model and relevant for multiple low-level QGs along the lifecycle. Regarding QG Metrics, information on the use case, stakeholder and medical domain are relevant not only for metrics selection and interpretation, but for data and thus model overall quality assessment, as well. Consequently, as relevant identified information is shared across QGs. Context-embedding includes medical evaluations, such as clinical information on label correlations, as well as considerations regarding imbalanced data sets, and other use case specific challenges and possible solutions from a technical and clinical perspective. From a management perspective, it is desirable to consider pre-selection steps before the debut of the implementation.

Intra-Selection aims to reassess previous design decisions and evaluate the chosen methods for suitability under consideration of the identified domain knowledge and based on concrete results of the first prototype. For QG Metrics, this includes the comparison of the metrics' performance against additional material such as prediction vs. true label distribution, for instance to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the selected metrics' performance. For the multi-label case, class probabilities offer important insights and should be considered from the start of designing the implementation. Possibly, with advancing research, different approaches than the previously selected baseline can appear reasonable and should be documented and analyzed further. Also, the definition of a bench-marking strategy, as well as long-term usability and stakeholder assessment should already be considered during this phase, in alignment with the most promising solution for the respective design decision.

Post-Selection is meant to optimize the selected approach and functions as a foundation for monitoring of the previous design decisions under consideration of stakeholder view-adapted representations of relevant information. In our case, we analyzed the metric-to-monitor in more detail and tuned the classification thresholds.

The empirically extracted and generalizable approach for design decision definition is characterized by inherent dynamics that are necessary for AI quality management. All stages are intended to result in documentation that builds the foundation for the next cycle, while especially intra- and post-selection are to be considered alternately until a satisfying performance and setup for auditing is achieved. Also, with respect to a long-term monitoring strategy, a crucial part of QG creation. Use case-specific information from pre-selection is expected to be less fluctuate, since it is based on the intended use of the system. Changes of which, result in a re-assessment from an official audit point of view according to the MDR.⁹

Our experiments partly concretize the process based on our previously introduced research questions towards reliable performance metrics for multi-label (ECG) classification and can be refined further. For instance, through the inclusion of fairness metrics as described by ISO on Bias in AI Systems and AI aided decision making as part of QG Metrics. Our empirically extracted method for multi-label (ECG) classification is illustrated in accordance with our proposed decision process and summarized on the following page.

⁹ Prinz, et al, Market access of continuous learning AI systems in medicine, p.7, VDE DGBMT, 2023

- a. **Data (Inter-dependency: Foundation)** – Focus: Label State
 1. Label distribution
 2. Label structure
 3. Label transformation
 4. ...
 - b. **Pre-Selection (Design Decision: Baseline)** – Focus: Performance Metrics
 1. Domain Embedding: use case analysis; disease prevalence; benefit matrix
 2. Metrics analysis: multi-label; confusion-matrix; ROC/PR AUC
 3. ...
 - c. **Intra-Selection (Design Decision: Reassessment)** – Focus: Performance Metrics
 1. Additional material
 2. Class probabilities
 3. Domain knowledge: ...
 4. ...
 - d. **Post-Selection (Design Decision: Optimization)** – Focus: Performance Metrics
 1. Metric-to-monitor
 2. Threshold optimization
 3. ...
 - e. **Deployment, Maintenance (Inter-dependency: Outlook)** – Stakeholder Views
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b-d illustrate the generalizable method for design decision-making: pre-, intra-, and post-selection steps consisting of research question related design decisions, as well as use case adapted considerations. Within the context of the presented folder structure, our results are in “QG_Process_Structure/1_QG Model/1_Evolution/2_QG Model Training/3_QG Metrics”.

Higher level QGs, as *a* and *e* are referenced in the context of lower level QGs with respect to design decision-specific interdependencies that influence *b-d*. Regarding QG Data, the label state is identified as adjustable for our experiments. Other necessary information on the data set is extracted from literature on Physionet, the utilized open-source ML data set. Regarding the lifecycle embedding of QG Metrics, performance metrics are consulted during multiple stages and referenced from several other QGs on the lower levels, which needs to be identified for referencing. For instance, performance metrics are a crucial part of hyper-parameter tuning and system monitoring which makes them a central element of the AI lifecycle flow. Intra- and post-selection are strongly correlated and should be reassessed and adapted accordingly during different cycles of the intelligent system’s evolution while in alignment with pre-selection results.

Finally, guiding questions are a fundamental part of QG realization in general and are meant to support a comprehensive assessment in favor of overall risk mitigation. Examples along the process stages include the following and are concretized in further detail in the corresponding paper.

- What is the intended clinical use and what suitable metrics and methods exist?
- How can metrics be interpreted correctly? Which additional information is necessary?

As of now, our approach is continuously being refined and aims to one day support the implementation of reliable AI through comprehensive lifecycle management that allows for generic and practical guidelines while considering use case and stakeholder specific requirements.